

PRONUNCIATION AND ITS ROLE IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Annotation: This article is devoted to pronunciation forms of the English language. There are the phonetic analysis, the role of letters, vowels and consonants, pronunciation is also considered separately in this scientific article. Specifically illustrated with examples.

Keywords: English, pronunciation, sounds, letters, dialect, words, vowels, consonants, spelling, articulation.

An important aspect in learning a language is pronunciation. Based on the explanatory dictionary of Dmitry Nikolaevich Ushakov, pronunciation is the pronunciation or articulation of speech sounds, that is, the reproduction of a particular sound using different parts of the oral cavity. Pronunciation in English plays one of the most important roles, but, unfortunately, correct English pronunciation is very rare even among foreign language teachers. Many people do not put as a basis and do not understand the importance of pronunciation, they prefer the grammar-translation system, which consists in the mechanical memorization of words and the study of rules. In fact, it is necessary to train English pronunciation from the very beginning of learning a foreign language. Otherwise, it will be quite difficult to correct and catch up on entrenched mistakes. Everyone faced the problem of pronunciation at the initial stages of learning a language. It is important from the beginning of training to master sound speech, to learn how to pronounce sounds the way native speakers do. A feature of solving this problem (pronunciation practice) is a large time expenditure. It must be understood that without the correct pronunciation it is impossible to fully and perfectly master the language. The main goal of acquiring the correct pronunciation in a particular language (in our case, it is English) is the knowledge and excellent use of orthoepic norms in practice, as well as the development of the ability not only to hear, but also to understand the speech of a native speaker, so that this does not cause no difficulty in understanding. Let's not forget about the phonetic features of the English language, namely, how to formalize the English pronunciation intonation, which members of the sentence are stressed and which are unstressed, and so on. According to modern linguists, as a result of

the fact that the world community has entered the era of globalization, the processes that are closely related to the development and formation of linguistic culture are acquiring new features and developing at a fairly rapid pace. Nowadays, it is perfectly normal to meet a person who speaks his native language and, in addition, English. English has become a kind of professional and everyday standard of the communicative sphere of all mankind. For many people living in Europe and Asia, English is the second language of business or everyday life, or is used for other purposes. Before you fully immerse yourself in the English language, read and, with all this, pronounce words correctly, you need to study the transcription of English letters, given that in English pronunciation everything is different than in Russian. In Russian, "how a word is written is how it is pronounced." In English, almost always every word does not correspond to how it looks in writing. Some English words in writing are reflected in the same way, but their pronunciation is completely different (it depends on the context), while some, on the contrary, are pronounced exactly the same, but at the same time they have completely different meanings and are written differently. Based on all this, everyone who studies English must, first of all, understand how to read transcription signs. Without knowledge of these fundamentals, the student will not be able to move forward in learning the language, and one should not forget about the exceptions that "fill the expanses" of the English language. Pronunciation can be of two main types - phonological and phonetic. In phonological pronunciation, it is important to maintain the minimum of features, the non-observance of which can lead to misunderstanding. This is a "rough" pronunciation, without any subtleties, in fact, based on the native language with some innovations that a foreign language necessarily requires.

For example, the English phrase "I'm not going to see him again" can be phonologically pronounced something like this: Aym 'not 'goying tu 'si him e gen' Or Aim 'not 'gowing tu 'si him a gene'. It is in this way that foreign pronunciation is presented in bilingual phrasebooks. And it is at this level that tourists most often speak. Here it is important not to replace the essential feature of a foreign language with any of the native languages. For example, for a Russian speaker, a different degree of mouth opening (drooping of the lower jaw) does not play a semantic role (compare: "children" and "these"), in English - with a slight opening of the mouth, [e] is pronounced, and with a greater lowering of the lower jaw - [æ]. Wrong emphasis also makes it difficult to get the right information. So the word "written", pronounced with the accent on the second syllable, can be perceived as "retain", and the word "comfortable" - with the emphasis on "com"

and "ta" can be heard as "come for a table". The English language has its own specific rhythm, and if the speaker neglects it, this also leads to speech distortion. It's like trying to dance a polka or a foxtrot to a waltz tune. The effectiveness of communication involves guessing the listener's intentions of the interlocutor. In this case, the intonation of the message acquires a special role, with the help of which the speaker can express his intentions, for example, request information or confirm it, agree or object. In phonetic pronunciation, it is necessary to preserve both the semantic features of a foreign language and all its articulatory subtleties. Here, no detail can be superfluous: the position of the tip of the tongue during the articulation of sounds, the degree of aspiration, duration, the influence of the processes of interaction of sounds, the nature of syllable division, rhythmic organization, the variability of the prosodic structure, and many other factors. [1, p. 7-9]

Articulatory organs play a primary role in speech communication. At the same time, it is important to remember that, as such, articulatory organs proper do not exist, and the articulation of speech sounds is a secondary function of the organs of respiration, swallowing, chewing, and charm. From the point of view of speech production, these organs represent the speech apparatus. The speech apparatus consists of mobile and fixed organs of speech. The first group includes: 1) tongue, 2) lips, 3) soft palate with a small tongue, 4) posterior wall of the pharynx (pharynx), 5) vocal cords located in the larynx, 6) lower jaw. The immovable organs of speech include: 1) upper lips, 2) alveoli (a tubercle located directly behind the upper teeth), 3) hard palate. [2, p. 16] The pronunciation or reading of English words is not a process of spelling words. More often this is the result of converting letter combinations into sounds. Additional complications arise from the fact that many rules have exceptions. In such cases, the transcription in the dictionary will tell you the correct sound of the word. In addition, when learning English, working with a dictionary takes up a significant part of the time, and knowing the basic rules of reading makes it optimal.[3, p. 77]

It is also necessary to take into account the fact that in English articulation, that is, the pronunciation of vowels, is almost not influenced by consonants. The vowel is the leading sound in articulation. In this regard, it is recommended to combine as many different consonants as possible with a vowel when setting up an English pronunciation. In Russian, the articulation of vowels, to a greater extent, depends on the hardness or softness of neighboring consonants: "ox" - "led"; "nose" - "carried"[4]. The number of sounds in English is a matter of dispute among linguists around the world. The fundamental difference is not so great, but

there are a great many points of view on this issue. The classical theory identifies 44 sounds in English: 20 vowels and 24 consonants. Most of the sounds in English have analogues in Russian, some are almost identical, but there are also those whose equivalent, even with a strong desire, cannot be found. As a rule, the most difficult for English learners are the interdental consonants [θ] and [ð]. Pronunciation in English plays one of the most important roles, but, unfortunately, correct English pronunciation is very rare even among foreign language teachers. Many people do not put as a basis and do not understand the importance of pronunciation, they prefer the grammar-translation system, which consists in the mechanical memorization of words and the study of rules. In fact, it is necessary to train English pronunciation from the very beginning of learning a foreign language. Otherwise, it will be quite difficult to correct and catch up on entrenched mistakes. Everyone faced the problem of pronunciation at the initial stages of learning a language. It is important from the beginning of training to master sound speech, to learn how to pronounce sounds the way native speakers do. A feature of solving this problem (pronunciation practice) is a large time expenditure. It must be understood that without the correct pronunciation it is impossible to fully and perfectly master the language. The main goal of acquiring the correct pronunciation in a particular language (in our case, it is English) is the knowledge and excellent use of orthoepic norms in practice, as well as the development of the ability not only to hear, but also to understand the speech of a native speaker, so that this does not cause no difficulty in understanding. Let's not forget about the phonetic features of the English language, namely, how to formalize the English pronunciation intonation, which members of the sentence are stressed and which are unstressed, and so on. According to modern linguists, as a result of the fact that the world community has entered the era of globalization, the processes that are closely related to the development and formation of linguistic culture are acquiring new features and developing at a fairly rapid pace. Nowadays, it is perfectly normal to meet a person who speaks his native language and, in addition, English. English has become a kind of professional and everyday standard of the communicative sphere of all mankind. For many people living in Europe and Asia, English is the second language of business or everyday life, or is used for other purposes.

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In the case of the English sound [θ], Russian sounds [s] or [f] are usually obtained. Instead of [ð] sound [h] or [v]. This mistake is quite understandable, because in the Russian language there are no sounds, when pronouncing which you need to clamp your tongue between your teeth. Next comes a rather complex and incomprehensible sound [ŋ]. It is quite difficult to explain the pronunciation of this sound - in some way it looks like a soft [n '], but at the same time, it is pronounced not so much in the mouth as through the nose. Another complex sound is the sound [w]. When pronouncing it, the lips are rounded and something similar to the Russian sound [y] is obtained, but only more energetic. Further it is worth mentioning the plosives [p, t, k]. Their difficulty is that they are pronounced with some aspiration at the beginning, hence their name. The next sound that deserves attention is the sound [h]. Contrary to a common mistake, it is not pronounced like the Russian sound [x]. To pronounce it correctly, try to exhale lightly through your mouth. When you breathe on the glass to draw a funny face on it, you get exactly the sound that we need. The remaining consonants are generally similar to Russian ones, although they have their own characteristic features. With vowels in English, everything is much simpler. Most of them have analogues in Russian, but despite this, you should always pay attention to the shades of sound, because there are no trifles in learning a foreign language, every detail is important. [5] Thus, we can conclude that pronunciation plays one of the most key roles in learning English. Unfortunately, our speech apparatus is not initially tailored to the system of any particular language. That is why learning English along with your native language at an early age gives a

huge advantage in all aspects of learning it, including pronunciation. But this does not mean that at a later age it will be impossible to shape the sound base of the new language system. It is very possible, you just need to make it clear to yourself that in English there are sounds that have no analogue in Russian, and even those that are similar at first glance are fraught with many difficulties, since even in them you need to pay attention to differences in shades of sound

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